
Project Title: Brain Effects on Appetite and Metabolism (BEAM) Study

Introduction

Previous studies show that a high-fat diet in rodents causes inflammation and a cellular response, known as gliosis, within hypothalamic regions regulating energy balance and glucose homeostasis (1). Evidence suggests that gliosis plays a pathogenic role in obesity because, among other reasons, its development precedes weight gain (2,3). Importantly, gliosis is detectable in mice and humans by magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) (1,4,5). Using MRI, our group discovered the first evidence of gliosis in adults and children with obesity (1,6). It remains unknown whether gliosis presence has implications for eating behavior that could promote weight gain and eventual obesity (7). We therefore conducted a multi-site longitudinal cohort study in children to discover 1) if hypothalamic gliosis in children is associated with altered brain appetitive processing. Children were recruited at 2 sites in Seattle, WA and Baltimore, MD, underwent imaging and behavioral testing, and then returned for follow-up weight and other measurements over 1 year.

Aims & Hypotheses

Determine if central nervous system (CNS) appetitive processing is altered in children when evidence of hypothalamic gliosis is present. We therefore hypothesize that greater hypothalamic gliosis in children will be associated with greater post-meal activation by high-calorie visual food cues in brain regions involved in appetitive processing.

Data Collection Procedures

This is a longitudinal cohort study that recruited 101 children (9-11 years old), balanced by sex and from different weight groups (healthy weight, overweight, with obesity), using online and print advertising from the Greater Seattle, WA and Baltimore, MD Areas.

Inclusion criteria were:

- Children aged 9-11 years from the general population in Seattle, WA and Baltimore, MD
- BMI \geq 15th percentile for age and sex

Exclusion criteria were:

- Significant health conditions including type 2 diabetes
- History of major weight loss over the past year (approximately 10 lbs or more, not due to illness)
- History of eating disorder
- Current use of medications known to alter appetite, body weight, or brain response (e.g., anti-epileptics, glucocorticoids, antipsychotics, stimulants for ADHD)
- Documented cognitive disorder
- MRI contraindication (i.e., braces, claustrophobia)
- Weight > 330 pounds (MRI limit)
- Severe food allergies, vegetarian, or vegan, or unable to consume study foods
- Currently in formal weight loss program

Single-site IRB Approval was obtained from Johns Hopkins Medicine IRB under the number 00210835.

Measured Variables

Outcome measures:

Primary: Functional MRI global average of parameter estimates across our *a priori* Regions of Interest (ROIs) involved in appetitive processing (see below) pre- and post- standardized meal. Primary contrast of interest: High-calorie foods > Objects; Secondary contrasts: High-calorie > Low-calorie foods; Low-calorie foods > Objects.

Secondary: Parameter estimates within individual ROIs.

Predictor measures:

Mean bilateral T2 relaxation time from the mediobasal hypothalamus (MBH). A tertile approach will be used to define Low vs High gliosis groups. Details on the methodology to assess evidence of MBH gliosis can be found in prior publications (5,6,8).

Covariate measures:

Study site, biological sex, and pubertal status.

Percentage of standardized meal (pre-load meal) consumed.

Experimental Design

Pre and Post-meal task functional MRI were acquired.

The first MRI occurred while subjects were fasted (after overnight fasting). After the pre-meal MRI session, subjects exited the scanner, ate a standardized macaroni and cheese meal to stimulate satiety, and then returned to the scanner for a second (post-meal) scan about 30 minutes post-meal. We titrated caloric load to 30% of estimated daily caloric needs using a calculation for resting energy expenditure (Mifflin-St. Jeor equation (9)) and an activity factor (1.3). Serial Visual Analog Scale (VAS) ratings assessed subjective appetite. After each scanning session, subjects viewed a selection of photographs of objects and foods, some of which they may have seen in the scanner and were asked to indicate whether they saw them while in the MRI (Post-test to assess attention to images). Thirty-two pictures were included (16 objects, 8 high-calorie foods, and 8 low-calorie foods) with 50% in each category as distracter images. Additionally, another set of food images were shown after each scanning session and subjects were asked to rate how appealing those foods were to them at that time (Appeal ratings).

Previously validated and child-friendly images were commercial-quality stock photographs and were grouped into four categories: high-calorie foods (e.g., desserts, pizza, burgers), low-calorie foods (e.g., fruits, vegetables, lean meats), nonfood objects (e.g., sports equipment, household items, clothing items), and scrambled images (pixelated images created from images presented in other blocks, not recognizable). Each fMRI session (pre-meal and post-meal) included a distinct set of 15 blocks with 10 images each presented for 2.4 seconds. Nonfood object blocks (n = 6) alternated with high-calorie (n = 3), low-calorie (n = 3) food, and scrambled (n=3) blocks and the order was counterbalanced across participants (half viewed high-calorie images as the first food block). All food images were ready to eat (i.e., fruits were depicted peeled), were displayed on a gray background, were equal in size (600 x 400 dpi), and were matched for luminosity across blocks.

Participants were encouraged to pay attention to the screen, and think about how the food would taste if they ate it or how the object would feel if they touched it.

Data acquisition

Participant preparation:

The mock scan training (~15 minutes) consisted of participants being oriented to the mock scanner, given the opportunity to listen to the ambient (scanner) noise, getting ‘suited up’ and loaded in, and training to encourage participants to lie still. Participants practiced the functional MRI task (picture viewing). The practice pictures were of trees and flowers (none of which were shown during the food cue task).

MRI system and acquisition:

Scans were acquired with a 32-channel SENSE head coil on a 3-Tesla Philips Achieva MR System with Software Version 5.1.7 (Philips Medical Systems, Best, The Netherlands) with dual Quasar gradients (80mT/m at a slew rate of 110 mT/m/s or 40 mT/m at a slew rate of 220 mT/m/s). In both sessions, a 306 volume, T2*-weighted single-shot echo-planar imaging (EPI) timeseries (51 ascending axial slices, 2.5 mm isotropic voxels, repetition time (TR)=1200 ms, echo time (TE)=30 ms, Flip angle=70 degrees, SENSE factor=3) was acquired during passive picture viewing.

A multi-band (MB) APA (TR/TE=1200/30 ms, flip angle=70 degrees, SENSE factor=3), and spin-echo APA and APP (TR=5000 ms, TE=60 ms, flip angle=90 degrees), with the same geometry as the functional scans, allowed for distortion correction of the EPI data. A 3D Compressed Sense Magnetization-Prepared Rapid Gradient-Echo (MPRAGE) image with 176 sagittal slices (TR=7.9, TE=3.6 ms, flip angle=7°, CS-SENSE factor=3, matrix=240 x 240, 1 mm isotropic voxels) was acquired for registration of the functional data to standard space.

Preprocessing

Anatomical T1 images will be processed using FSL version 6.0.7 (Functional MRI of the Brain (FMRIB) Software Library, www.fmrib.ox.ac.uk/fsl) (10) and FreeSurfer version 7.3.2 (<http://surfer.nmr.mgh.harvard.edu/>) (11). FSL’s `fsl_anat` command will be used to perform the following operations: 1) reorientation images to MNI orientation; 2) apply RF/B1-inhomogeneity-correction; 3) linear registration to MNI space; 4) brain extraction; 5) segmentation of grey matter, white matter, and cerebrospinal fluid; 6) segmentation of subcortical structures. FreeSurfer’s `recon-all` command will be used to generate white matter and ventricular masks to be used later in functional image processing, which will be run using its `SynthStrip` and `SynthSeg` options (12,13). Following these commands, FreeSurfer’s `mri_cnr` command will be used to determine which available T1 scan possess the highest contrast-to-noise ratio. This T1 and its computed outputs from FSL and FreeSurfer will subsequently be used for both time points.

Timeseries data will be processed using tools from FSL version 5.0.9 (Functional MRI of the Brain (FMRIB) Software Library, www.fmrib.ox.ac.uk/fsl) (10) and Analysis of Functional NeuroImages (AFNI, <http://afni.nimh.nih.gov/afni>) (14). The functional data will be preprocessed with the following steps: 1) elimination of the first three and last three timepoints to allow magnetization to reach steady state; 2) simultaneous slice-timing and motion correction (15); 3) mask-based removal of non-brain tissue removal with the Brain Extraction Tool (BET) (16); 4) detrending via bandpass filtering with FSL; 5) field-inhomogeneity distortion correction using FSL’s `topup` command with two reversed phase encoded images (missing images n=6 participants); 6) nuisance regression of motion artifacts quantified using principal

component analysis (PCA) and physiological noise quantified using component-based noise correction (CompCor) (17); 7) linear registration to MNI space; 8) Gaussian spatial smoothing (FWHM=5mm) and subsequent application of a 2mm MNI brain mask.

The registration matrix and warp field for each timeseries to the participant's skull-stripped high-resolution structural scan will be calculated using boundary-based registration in FSL incorporating the unwrapped phase image implemented in `epi_reg` (18–21). The structural scans will then be registered to the Montreal Neurological Institute template space (ICBM152) the diffeomorphic registration in the ANTs toolkit (22,23). For each participant, the derived transformations to register functional images to MNI space will be applied to the statistical images for analyses.

Statistical modeling

A priori thresholds for excessive motion were defined as frame-wise displacement (FD) > 1 and motion outliers as activation greater than 1.5 times the interquartile range, > 15% of total volumes. Using the FMRI Expert Analysis Tool (FEAT), the time series statistical analysis will be performed with FMRIB's Improved Linear Model with local autocorrelation correction (24) to each participant's subject-level data. The regression model will include predictors for the stimulus conditions, as well as nuisance covariates (the first principal components of the six rigid-body motion parameters and their first derivatives, the average time-series from eroded (1 mm in 3D) masks of the lateral ventricles and white matter derived from running FreeSurfer on the T1-weighted image, and single-point regressors accounting for individual motion spikes defined as framewise displacement greater than 3 mm or temporal derivative of time-course variance over voxels (DVARS) outliers identified with FSL's motion outliers (25) and non-physiologic spikes. To allow for variation in the BOLD response over time, each block of the stimulus conditions will be modeled separately by using a boxcar, convolved with a gamma function and its temporal derivative.

The condition effects will be estimated from the average response across blocks for each contrast of interest (high-calorie foods vs. low-calorie foods, high-calorie foods vs. objects, low-calorie foods vs. objects, and objects vs. scrambled). *A priori* ROIs within an extended satiety network, medial orbitofrontal cortex, and substantia nigra/ventral tegmental area, and bilateral regions of the amygdala, dorsal striatum, ventral striatum, insula, that were previously shown to be markers of satiety or predictors of food choice were selected (26,27). ROI masks will be determined by functional-anatomic criteria including responsiveness to food cues (food vs. object, pre- and post-meal; whole-brain; $P < 0.05$ uncorrected) and then anatomically restricted with a minimum criterion of 25% from the Harvard-Oxford probabilistic atlas (28). This results in the exclusion of voxels with no measurable activation by food cues. The substantia nigra/ventral tegmental area (SN/VTA) will be determined by the same functional-anatomic criteria and be anatomically defined as previously done (26,29).

Mean activation within each region for the contrasts of interest will be extracted using these functional-anatomic ROI masks. Regional parameter estimates will be averaged across *a priori* brain regions to obtain a single measure of average activation for each subject, pre- and post-meal in an extended satiety network. To investigate potential group differences within individual regions, region-specific analyses will be performed.

The primary statistical analysis approach will be by linear or logistic regression or a method that can accommodate repeated measures or missing data if required such as a Generalized Estimating Equation (GEE) or linear mixed models. Interaction terms will evaluate region*group differences where region is hypothalamus or control regions in putamen and amygdala to assess region-specific effects of group (low

and high MBH gliosis) and time (pre- and post-meal mean activation in an extended satiety network) using a statistical threshold of $\alpha=0.05$.

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